

THE COMBINATION OF NATIONAL AND RELIGIOUS VALUES IN CENTRAL ASIAN HISTORY

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Annotation: *This article is aimed at highlighting the specifics of the national and religious values of the peoples of Central Asia, who have centuries-old traditions, culture, language, religious beliefs and lifestyles.*

Keywords: *religious views, customs, spiritual life, religious tolerance, spiritual values, values.*

Introduction.

As most countries in the world are multi-ethnic and multi-religious, Uzbekistan is one of those countries. Universal values such as inter-ethnic harmony and inter-religious tolerance have their deep roots in it.

The region of Central Asia, in particular, Uzbekistan, is a land inhabited by several dissimilar peoples with different customs, culture, language, and lifestyle, who believe in different religions. . The fact that Uzbekistan is located at the intersection of important trade routes from a geographical point of view, and has economic and cultural relations with many countries, has had a great impact on the religious and cultural life of the local people. Feelings such as honoring a person and valuing others, respecting elders and honoring others, regardless of nationality and religious views, are high qualities of the peoples of Central Asia. It is these factors that form the moral basis of not only spiritual and educational, but also religious tolerance of our people.

In turn, the geographical position between the Amudarya and Syrdarya rivers made it possible for ancient Eastern, Hellenic, Western Iranian, Turkish, and Chinese cultures to actively cooperate in the center of the region of great civilizations.¹.

¹ Мирзаев Р. Фердинанд Рихтгофен – “Буюк Ипак йўли” атамасининг асосчиси // Мозийдан садо. – Тошкент, 2005. № 2 (25). – Б. 42-45.

It can be seen that Islam and other religions and cultures have developed in harmony in the land of Uzbekistan since time immemorial and made an incomparable contribution to the spiritual development of the society.

Results.

It is mentioned in many historical sources that our country is one of the oldest countries where the first religious views and ideas appeared. Religions with a complex ideological system, such as Zoroastrianism, Buddhism, Judaism, and Christianity, have been peacefully operating in the region since ancient times. Ancient graves in Teshik-Tosh caves, Buddhist finds in Fayoz and Kara-Tepa, remains of Dalvarzintepa and Sugdiyana, and the results of research currently being conducted in cooperation with French and Japanese archaeologists are confirmation of our opinion.²

Ph.D., prof. A. Hasanov stated that in ancient times there was no religious enmity between peoples and peoples. Every state, every city, every tribe of the inhabitants of the ancient world worshiped its local chief deity and many other deities representing the forces of the universe and nature. Although these gods are similar to each other, they are called by different names in the language of each nation. At the end of ancient times, as a great achievement of the human spirit and a real revolution of the worldview, the last stage of Judaism, such as Christianity, Zoroastrianism and Islam, appeared as ethical (based on high morals) religions. But at the same time, they were not called dogmatic (dogmatic) religions for nothing, which created mutual religious disagreements and competition between peoples. They began to believe that each of these religions has only one god (that is, a god specific to this religion), and that the gods of others are nothing but idols. Even among the representatives of the same religion, there was a division between "true and false". So, for almost 2,000 years, bloody conflicts have been going on in the path of "true faith" on Earth. Due to a happy coincidence, it can be said that the history of Uzbekistan was an exception to this "general rule", that is, we have not had a single war on religious grounds.³

Tolerance, a characteristic of our people from time immemorial, did not appear suddenly, it is traditional for us. If we take a brief look at the

² Қаранг: Дервиш Р.А., Левтеев Л.Г., Мусакаева А. Памятники истории религии и культуры в Узбекистане. – Т.: Ўқитувчи, 1994. – С. 10-12, 56-60.

³ Ҳасанов А. Ўзбекистонда диний бағрикенгликнинг тарихий аънаналари // Жаҳолатга қарши маърифат – тинчлик ва барқарорлик асоси. – Т.:Тошкент ислом университети, 2003. – Б. 40-41.

religious history of Uzbekistan, we can see that the current territory of Uzbekistan is one of the oldest countries where the first religious ideas and beliefs appeared in people. In the middle of the Stone Age, worship of various animals and the Sun spread among our ancestors, and later fetishism, animism, witchcraft (magic)⁴.

In the conditions of Central Asia, there were various conflicts between sedentary farming and nomadic herding typical of the Zoroastrian way of life. He later made a great contribution to the development of monotheistic ideas. After all, "Zoroaster started a new stage in the history of human spirituality by calling people to worship Ahuramazda. First, he stepped into monotheism, which is the opposite of polytheism, i.e., a higher stage of religious belief. Secondly, while before men worshiped the gods in terror, powerless before their terrible destructive power, now Zarathustra is full of compassion for men, exhorting them to good, after their death. called to pray to Ahuramazda, the god who can provide eternal prosperity"⁵.

In various historical, scientific and literary sources, "Avesta" is interpreted as "Guide to Life", "Admonition", "Collection of Laws", "Complex of Knowledge". "Avesta" provides valuable information about the socio-economic life, religious views, perception of the world and people, customs and values of the peoples of Turan, Khorasan, Azerbaijan, Mesopotamia, Iran, and Asia Minor in the ancient period before Christ. is the source.

At the same time, we must say that the period of invasion led by Alexander the Great, who ordered the destruction of all copies of "Avesta", is proof that people were forced into foreign religions in the history of the region. Of course, the invaders tried to destroy the ideas reflected in the sacred source in order to spread their thoughts and ideas.

As a result of Tsarist Russia's occupation of Turkestan in the middle of the 19th century, national and spiritual values began to suffer. Among other negative results of the establishment of the colonial administration system, people's pride, national pride and religious beliefs were violated. Such actions were continued during the former Soviet rule. The government, armed with an atheistic ideology, from the very first days of its existence, started a determined fight against religion, including Islam.⁶

⁴ Ўзбекистон – диний бағрикенглик ўлкаси // Бағрикенглик – барқарорлик ва тараққиёт омили. – Т.:Тошкент ислом университети, 2007. – Б. 101.

⁵ Зардуштийлик // Фалсафа. Комусий луғат. – Т.: “Ўзбекистон файласуфлари” миллий жамияти, 2004. – Б. 131.

⁶ Қаранг: Keller. Shoshana // Islam in Soviet Central Asia 1917-1927 : Soviet Policy and the Struggle for Control. – Central Asian Survey, 1993/1, XI. – P. 27-28.

During the Kushan and Hephthalite states, Buddhism entered the territory of Uzbekistan directly from India and took root. V. Litvinsky stated that in Central Asia "Buddhism penetrated even the house of the craftsman and the hut of the laborer."⁷.

The introduction of Buddhism from India to Central Asia is usually associated with the rule of the Kushans. During the reign of Emperor Kanishka (end of the 1st century - beginning of the 2nd century), the Kushan kingdom became one of the centers of this religion. For example, the coins minted by Kanishka include the image of Buddha along with other deities. According to the Chinese Xuan-Zian, at the beginning of the 7th century, 10 Buddhist monasteries (sangarama) and a thousand monks were active in Termez.

At the beginning of the 20th century, on the right bank of the Amudarya, many precious metals belonging to Buddhism were found - a large number of coins made of gold or silver, small sculptures and other monuments.⁸.

The roots of tolerance and compromise go back centuries. According to Kato, a Japanese scientist who conducts research on the culture of different religions that worked in the territory of our republic, it is no surprise to anyone that the unique monuments of Buddhist culture discovered in the Surkhandarya oasis, Jewish monuments, and Christian shrines in Bukhara stand alongside Islamic monuments in our country.

All religions of the world are based on the ideals of goodness and rely on qualities such as goodness, peace, friendship. Religion calls people to honesty and purity, kindness, brotherhood and tolerance. Most religions consider this world to be transient. They promote the idea that the real purpose of human life is to do good and meritorious deeds in this world and prepare for the trials of the eternal world. In all religions, the essence and content of human life, the establishment of political-legal and moral relations between people based on the criteria of equality and justice are reflected. Christianity, one of the world's religions, promotes universal human values such as generosity, compassion, love for one's loved ones, sympathy, and forgiveness, imbued with humanitarian ideas.

⁷ Ўзбекистон – диний бағрикенглик ўлкаси // Бағрикенглик – барқарорлик ва тараққиёт омили. – Т.: Тошкент ислом университети, 2007. – Б. 101.

⁸ Қаранг: Диний экстремизм ва терроризмга қарши курашнинг маънавий-маърифий асослари. – Т.: Тошкент ислом университети, 2005. – Б. 30.

At the same time, Buddhism explains the causes of suffering, how to get rid of them, and shows the way to end suffering, that is, to reach the state of nirvana.⁹.

Ўзбекистон ҳудудида зардуштийлар билан бир қаторда буддавийликка эътиқод қилувчилар ҳам яшаганлар. Милоднинг биринчи асрларидан бошлаб, Самарқанд ва Бухорога кириб келган яҳудийлар жамоалари вакиллари ҳозирга қадар ўз динларига эркин эътиқод қилиб келмоқдалар¹⁰.

It is known that Judaism is a national religion, and a number of ideals of goodness and tolerance are promoted in it. In particular, in Judaism, the 10 commandments that Yahweh presented to Moses on Mount Sinai included the following: not to worship other than Yahweh, the only god; not to create a god in the earth, sky and water; that is, not to worship idols, dates; honoring the Sabbath and consecrating it to God; honor parents; non-murder; not to mention God's name in vain; not to steal; not to commit adultery; not to bear false witness to one's relatives; not to look at the property of their loved ones. These religious and moral criteria are among the factors that decorate human spirituality.

It is not surprising that the residence of representatives of the Jewish religion in our country is another high example of Uzbek tolerance, ethnic, cultural and religious tolerance. In particular, R. Bensman, one of the representatives of the Jewish community, commented on this, noting that the first synagogue in Bukhara was built in the 8th century, and at that time, along with representatives of other religions, conditions were created for free belief in their own religion, "Judaism persecuted in medieval Europe and the Byzantine Empire. In Central Asia, it had the same rights as other religions"¹¹, – he writes.

In addition to the above-mentioned religions, communities of Jews, monists, and Mazdakians lived in some parts of Uzbekistan.

"Almost 1.5 thousand years ago, Istami (552-576), who sat on the throne of the Western Turkic khanate, which includes the present Central Asia, was known as a tolerant ruler. During this period, religious thinking in the Turkic tribes reached the highest level of development, and the worship of the

⁹ Пупар П. Религии. – М.: Весь Мир, 2003. – С. 92.

¹⁰ Ибрагимов Э. Ўзбекистон – диний бағрикенглик ўлкаси // Ўзбекистон – бағрикенг диёр. – Т.: Ўзбекистон, 2007. – Б. 69.

¹¹ Бенсман Р. Деятельность религиозных организаций по укреплению межрелигиозного согласия // Межрелигиозное согласие – важное условие углубления демократических процессов в странах Центральной Азии (на примере Республики Узбекистан). Материалы международной конференции. – Ташкент, 2002. – С. 125-126.

main god - God - began on a large scale. Nevertheless, Istami-Hakhan allowed all the religions known in the country to freely follow.¹²

Among the religions that existed in our country before Islam, the Nestorian sect of Christianity, which entered via Sham (Syria) and Iran, took a significant place. The Christian communities also included representatives of some nomadic Turkic tribes, such as the Guz and the Togghiz. According to Academician V. Bartold, there was a Christian bishop in Samarkand in the 6th century and a metropolitan immediately before the arrival of the Arabs. There was also a Christian population in the territory of today's Tashkent and Khorezm regions.

In a number of scientific literature, it is interpreted that Christianity entered Central Asia in the 3rd century. This is connected with the persecution of the representatives of this religion in Iran and their migration to other regions. Shapur I, the king of Iran (241-272 years), settled the captured Roman soldiers in the eastern lands. There were Christians among them. In some written sources, it is noted that a diocese was established in Marv in 334. This indicates that Christians appeared in Marv earlier than 334 years ago and formed large communities.

So, in the early centuries of Christ, although Nestorians mainly entered Central Asia, especially Marv and Bactria, among them there were representatives of the Orthodox Church, Jacobites belonging to the direction of the military Syrian Church. Marv bishops gained great attention in the Eastern Church and participated in Church cathedrals¹³. After the Arabs entered these areas, the activities of the Christian communities gradually weakened. The second entry of Christians into Turkestan is connected with the conquest of the country by Tsarist Russia.

According to the Russian Orientalist V. Bartold, Islam entered Movarounnahr in the 8th century and began to harmonize with local religions and their specific values and customs.¹⁴. In turn, the peoples of Movarounnahr enriched Islam with their local moral ideas, legal norms and customs. This situation led to the acquisition of specific characteristics of Islam in Movarounnahr. This was not an accidental event in the atmosphere of comfortable tolerance that had formed by that time in the region.

Since the establishment of Islam, to this day, in Muslim countries where Islam is widespread, other true religions have been freely allowed. They

¹² Ҳасанов А. Ўзбекистонда диний бағрикенгликнинг тарихий аънаналари // Жаҳолатга қарши маърифат – тинчлик ва барқарорлик асоси. – Т.: Тошкент ислом университети, 2003. – Б. 41.

¹³ Қаранг: Ибрагимов Э. Ўзбекистон – диний бағрикенглик ўлкаси // Ўзбекистон – бағрикенг диёр. – Т.: Ўзбекистон, 2007. – Б. 70.

¹⁴ Бартольд В. Сочинения. - М., 1996. Т.6. – С. 105.

entered churches and synagogues and prayed freely. Even their rich souls were taken under the protection of the state.

According to historical sources, it is noted that in the past, there was not a single conflict on the basis of religious and ethnic relations in Uzbekistan. At this point, we must say that this reality can be clearly seen in the relations between Islam, Christianity, Judaism and other confessions operating in our country today. Summing up such friendly relations, President of the Republic Islam Karimov said: "The coexistence of Muslims and Christians on the land of Uzbekistan is a rare symbol of religious and spiritual harmony and the best example of tolerance towards representatives of all religions." clearly showed the reality.

In fact, the religion of Islam has devoted a lot of space to issues of peace and friendship among peoples, and it does not prohibit cooperation with those who believe in other religions. It is clearly stated in the Qur'an: "Allah will not prevent you from doing good and being fair to those who did not fight with you about religion and did not drive you out of your land. Verily, Allah loves the righteous."¹⁵.

In the Qur'an, it is emphasized that people of different religions and cultures live in harmony and cooperation on Earth, regardless of their religion, race, and nationality: "O people! Indeed, We created you from a single male (Adam) and a single female (Eve) and made you into nations and tribes so that you may know one another. Indeed, in the sight of Allah, the most honorable of you is the most pious. Verily, Allah is All-Knowing, All-Aware."¹⁶.

Discussion.

It can be seen that in the sacred and divine sources of every religion, universal human values such as not to kill, not to steal, not to bear false witness, not to destroy people, but on the contrary, solidarity, humanity, and tolerance are mentioned.

The culture of Central Asia, embodying the best achievements of the past, in turn, had a significant impact not only on the further development of Islamic culture, but also on the Western renaissance and the development of principles of tolerance on a global scale. Therefore, the cultural achievements of the peoples of our country are an integral part of not only Muslim, but also world culture. Imam Bukhari's collection of hadiths "al-Jami' as-sahih" (9th century) created during this period was recognized

¹⁵ "Мумтахана" сураси, 8-оят. (Қаранг: Қуръони карим: маъноларининг таржима ва тафсири /Таржима ва тафсир муаллифи: А.Мансуров. – Т.: Тошкент ислом университети, 2004. – Б . 550.

¹⁶ "Хужурот" сураси, 13-оят.

by his contemporaries as the best of traditional Sunni collections and is still one of the most important books of Muslims around the world. . The fact that the ideas that are the basis for religious bigotry and bigotry are not propagated in this book also served to give priority to the principles of social tolerance in the history of our country.¹⁷.

It is known that the Hanafi (Imam A'zam) sect settled and spread in Movarounnahr from the 9th century. This is probably not for nothing, because the sect of Imam Azam is distinguished from other sects by giving freedom to other religions and local customs. Our compatriots who perfected the teachings of Hanafi - scholars such as Imam Moturidi and Burhoniddin Marginani - made a great contribution to the elimination of ideological bias among Muslims, the stability of the Sunna direction of Islam, that is, the way of the people of Sunna and the community. added.

We should emphasize that the tolerance at that time was at the same time, on the one hand, religious scholars such as Imam Bukhari, Imam Termizi, i.e. possessors of divine thought, and on the other hand, secularists such as Farobi, Khorezmi, Beruni created a wide opportunity for thinkers who have acquired deep knowledge and put forward the idea of the priority of science values to live side by side and create.

Al-Khwarazmi's work "al-Jabr wal-muqabala", which describes the basics of algebra and arithmetic, was considered the main source of related sciences in Asia and Europe.

Ibn Sina's "Laws of Medicine" ("al-Qanun fit-tibb", 11th century) was the main guide to medicine both in the East and in the West until the 19th century. According to Ludwig F. Grunebaum, Ibn Sina's "Treatise of Love" ("ar-Risala fil-ishq") served as the basis for the feminine lyrics of medieval French travel poets¹⁸.

Mahmoud Zamakhshari's (XII century) commentary on the Qur'an is recognized as one of the best sources in this field. The author himself took the names "Jarullah" ("Man of God") and "Fakhr al-Khorazm" ("Pride of Khorazm"). The Arabs acknowledged that this non-Arab scholar taught them the Arabic language through his works and activities.¹⁹.

The invasion of the Mongols in the 13th century did not fail to affect the life of the peoples of Central Asia and the development of the Islamic

¹⁷ Қаранг: Хусниддинов З. Ўзбекистонда диний бағрикенглик. -Т.: “Тошкент ислом университети” нашриёт-матбаа бирлашмаси, 2006. -Б. 12.

¹⁸ Хусниддинов З. Ўзбекистонда диний бағрикенглик. -Т.: “Тошкент ислом университети” нашриёт-матбаа бирлашмаси, 2006. -Б. 12.

¹⁹ Уватов У. Махмуд аз-Замахшарий. – Т.: 1995. – Б. 25.

religion in the region. At that time, Sufism, formed in the region, played an important role in uniting the masses against the invaders.

It is known that science and culture, which had declined during the almost two-century rule of the Mongols, were restored to their former glory thanks to the great reformist policy of Amir Temur. However, after Sahibgiron's death, political conflicts and struggles for the throne began to escalate among the Timurids. At such a time, Sufis protected the fate of the country and the interests of the people.

During the period of Timurids, Islam became important in the socio-political and cultural life of Movarounnahr. The monuments built by Amir Temur still adorn our country and are considered to be original examples of world architecture. Gori-Amir, Registan Ensemble, Bibikhanim have become an expression of the high historical construction culture and art of Uzbekistan. It is recorded in historical sources that representatives of many nationalities and different sects took part in their construction²⁰.

We should highlight one situation, "the existence of mosques, churches and synagogues in our big cities for centuries, the fact that people of different nationalities and religions have been freely practicing their religious practices is a confirmation of this. The fact that there were no conflicts between them on a religious basis even in the most difficult and difficult periods of our history indicates that our nation has accumulated great experience in religious tolerance.²¹ In turn, religious tolerance has always served as a special shield against hostility in social life.

Doctor of Philosophy, Professor A. Ochildiyev stated that "it (that is, religious tolerance) is a way for the coexistence of different faiths in the same time and space, the formation of cooperation and solidarity between their carriers. opened This, in turn, served the peace and development of the country, the development of universal culture and spirituality.²²

Archbishop Vladimir said that in the 19th century, when the peasants who were forcibly relocated from the central regions of Russia fell into a desperate situation, the local population provided them with all possible assistance. Hieromonk Khariton, who saw the events of that time, testified that "the local population treated the poor settlers with compassion, without which most of them would have died of hunger and poverty."

²⁰ Хусниддинов З. Ўзбекистонда диний бағрикенглик. -Т.: "Тошкент ислом университети" нашриёт-матбаа бирлашмаси, 2006. - Б. 13.

²¹ Миллий истиқлол ғояси: асосий тушунча ва тамойиллар. – Т.: Ўзбекистон, 2000. – Б. 61.

²² Очилдиев А. Миллий ғоя ва миллатлараро муносабатлар. – Т.: Ўзбекистон, 2004. – Б. 92.

The Russian Orthodox priests who came to the lands of Turkestan did not focus on missionary work, but on meeting the religious needs of their communities. It is known that the local Muslim population helped when the Orthodox built the church. For example, local imams and merchants donated money to the construction of the "Holy Georgiy" temple in Chirchik. This situation is proof that mutual respect between the representatives of these religions was formed from those times.

By the time of the Soviets, both Muslims and representatives of other religions were persecuted by the Bolsheviks. Many Orthodox priests were deported from Russia to Central Asia. About 3,000 deportees were placed behind the "Botkin" cemetery in Tashkent alone, and some witnesses say that almost every day Muslims came and distributed food and clothes to them. It is also known that sometimes Muslims risked their lives to protect the Orthodox from persecution. Suffering experienced together made people more united.

In general, history shows that the artificial separation of religious and secular principles, and the act of contrasting them with each other, leads to trouble. Religious extremism and terrorism have nothing to do with the true religion, which is based on high universal values, where religion has always encouraged people to increase good qualities and get rid of bad ones in every period of our country's history.

In today's complex process on the spiritual and religious fronts, representatives of all nationalities and religions adhere to the principles of solidarity, tolerance and mutual respect towards each other, one of the important factors of permanent stability.

Recently, growing religious fanaticism and militancy in the whole world, especially in our region, is causing actions contrary to tolerance, which is the true essence of Islam. The worldly development of states, democratic changes, and the process of religious tolerance are adversely affected by vices such as fanaticism, religious intolerance, and extremism.

Conclusion.

In short, the harmony of the national and religious values of our people with the values of the current democratic society is one of the important factors in the further development of our republic in the future and joining the world community.